

Evaluation in European educational projects: methodology and examples

Evaluación en proyectos educativos europeos: metodología y ejemplos

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Abstract

This article discusses the importance of evaluation in European educational projects, highlighting its essential role in all phases of the project life cycle: initial, ongoing and final. It presents methodologies for defining evaluation indicators related to resources, outcomes, activities and long-term impacts, differentiating between quantitative and qualitative indicators. In addition, it describes the use of instruments such as surveys, interviews and tests to collect data and measure results. On that basis, examples of both indicators and instruments are provided, looking at some possible uses in European educational projects. Within this framework, the EFQM model is explored as a comprehensive framework for quality assurance and continuous improvement in these projects. Finally, current limitations, recommendations for overcoming them and practical implications for the application of these approaches in future educational projects at European level are discussed.

Keywords: Education, Evaluation, European projects.

Resumen

Este artículo analiza la importancia de la evaluación en los proyectos educativos europeos, destacando su papel esencial en todas las fases del ciclo de vida del proyecto: inicial, en curso y final. Presenta metodologías para definir indicadores de evaluación relacionados con los recursos, resultados, actividades e impactos a largo plazo, matizando la diferencia entre indicadores cuantitativos y cualitativos. Además, se describe el uso de instrumentos como encuestas, entrevistas y pruebas para recopilar datos y medir resultados. Sobre esa base se proporcionan ejemplos tanto de indicadores como de instrumentos, viendo algunos posibles usos en proyectos educativos europeos. En ese marco, se explora el modelo EFQM como marco integral para el aseguramiento de la calidad y la mejora continua en estos proyectos. Por último, se discuten las limitaciones actuales, las recomendaciones para superarlas y las implicaciones prácticas de la aplicación de estos enfoques en futuros proyectos educativos a escala europea.

Palabras clave: Educación, Evaluación, Proyectos europeos.

1 Introduction

Evaluation plays a fundamental role in the innovation and improvement of educational centres, by providing key data and information that guide strategic decision-making (Casanova, 2023; Ministerio de Educación y Formación Profesional., 2023). Through the identification of strengths and areas for improvement, evaluation processes allow institutions to adjust their practices, adopt more efficient pedagogical approaches and align their resources with the real needs of the environment. In addition, evaluation fosters a culture of critical reflection and learning at the organizational level, which encourages experimentation and the implementation of innovative solutions (Rodríguez-Mantilla, 2021). For example, by assessing the impact of new technologies in the classroom, schools can identify which tools are best suited to improve learning, allowing them to optimize their use and extend their implementation. In this sense, evaluation not only serves to measure results, but also becomes a driver

of change and development, helping schools to continuously adapt to the challenges of a dynamic and globalized environment (Owen, 2020).

In the context of European educational programmes, evaluation has established itself as a crucial element in ensuring the success and sustainability of projects funded and promoted by the European Union and other organisations (European Commission, 2021, 2025a). These projects, which mainly seek to promote innovation and improve the quality of education, require a detailed analysis throughout their life cycle to verify that the resources, efforts and results are aligned with the objectives set and respond to the needs of the beneficiaries. Evaluation is not only a tool for control, but also for continuous improvement, especially through formative and summative methodologies that allow the adjustment of ongoing activities and the measurement of the final achievements achieved (European Commission, 2021; European Commission: European Parliament, 2017; European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation *et al.*, 2024).

The literature review shows that there are various evaluation approaches and frameworks developed at the European level, with studies emphasizing the importance of quality management models in the educational field. Among these, the *European Foundation for Quality Management* (EFQM) model (Fonseca *et al.*, 2021; Hakes, 2007; Martínez Mediano & Riopérez Losada, 2005; Nicolas & Del Castillo, 2020; Sütőová *et al.*, 2022) has positioned itself as a reference in quality Evaluation and continuous improvement, especially in the educational context. This model provides a structure for systematising and optimising evaluation processes and can be adapted to the specific characteristics of European educational projects, allowing institutions to establish a coherent framework for quality evaluation and monitoring.

The aim of this article is to analyse the methodologies and approaches applied in the evaluation of European educational projects, highlighting the role played by formative and final evaluation in the achievement of objectives and the impact of the project. Specific indicators are proposed that allow measuring various aspects such as the use of resources, the generation of products or results, the development of activities and the medium and long-term impacts. These

indicators are essential for a thorough analysis, as they provide quantitative and qualitative data that reflect both tangible results and the perception of quality of users and participants.

To this end, the evaluation in the life cycle of the projects is first reviewed, followed by the definition and structuring of evaluation indicators; evaluation instruments; EFQM model and its application in the evaluation of projects and case studies, to end with the discussion and conclusions in which recommendations for future projects are provided.

2 Project Lifecycle Evaluation

The evaluation of a European educational project is not a static process, but a dynamic cycle that accompanies the project from its beginning to its completion. This comprehensive approach allows results to be measured and improved continuously, ensuring that activities remain aligned with objectives and that the impact of the project is significant (Chen, 2015; Owen, 2020; Scriven, 2003; Stufflebeam, 2014). The role of each of the evaluation stages in the project life cycle is described below: the initial evaluation, the continuous or formative evaluation, and the final or summative evaluation (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Evaluation in the life cycle of projects (own elaboration)

2.1 Initial evaluation

The initial evaluation is a fundamental phase that takes place before the active implementation of the project. In this stage, the mission of the project is defined, the specific objectives to be achieved and a detailed planning of the activities to be carried out is carried out. This phase also includes the establishment of key indicators, which will allow the progress and success of the project to be measured in the subsequent stages. These indicators are designed according to the objectives, to guide the project towards clear and measurable results, both in the short, medium and long term.

The indicators defined at this early stage are essential to guide the development of the project and provide clear evaluation criteria for the formative and summative phases. For example, indicators can be defined related to the resources that will be used (such as funding and specific tools), the outputs or results that are expected to be generated (such as educational materials) and the processes that will be developed (such as training and dissemination activities). Proper planning and precise definition of indicators at this stage help to minimize risks and establish a solid basis for project monitoring.

2.2 Continuous or formative evaluation

Continuous evaluation, also known as formative evaluation, is carried out on a regular basis during the development of the project. Its purpose is to track progress and meeting objectives in real-time, allowing project managers to make timely adjustments to improve results and ensure that the project stays on track. This stage of the evaluation focuses on monitoring activities and processes, detecting problems or deviations, and adapting execution strategies when necessary (Patton, 2008).

This phase is especially useful for maintaining active communication between project participants and for promoting constant feedback, which improves the quality and effectiveness of the activities. For example, indicators such as the number of activities carried out, the number of participants involved, the level of skills acquired so far, and the quality of the materials generated can be evaluated. In this way, it provides a basis for informed decision-making, which allows

resources to be optimised and the approach to be adjusted according to the intermediate results obtained.

2.3 Final or summative evaluation

The final evaluation, or summative evaluation, is carried out at the end of the project and is aimed at measuring the overall impact achieved and the fulfilment of the proposed objectives. This phase focuses on analysing whether the project has managed to meet the needs and respond to the challenges posed at the beginning, as well as determining whether the results obtained are sustainable and replicable in other contexts. Summative evaluation allows the degree of success of the project and its contribution to the educational context in which it is implemented to be evaluated.

In this phase, both quantitative and qualitative indicators are used to analyse the outputs or results that have been carried out, the impact on the participants and the use of resources. Examples include an improvement in participants' competencies, the implementation of educational materials developed in institutions, and the level of end-user satisfaction. The results of the summative evaluation can also provide useful data for future initiatives and recommendations, to improve the effectiveness, efficiency and impact of European educational projects.

Together, the evaluation stages in the life cycle of a project offer a comprehensive vision that allows adjusting and improving the execution of the project in all its phases, ensuring that the objectives are met effectively and that the project leaves a positive and lasting impact in the educational field.

3 Definition and structuring of evaluation indicators

In order to properly evaluate European educational projects, it is essential to define specific indicators to measure the success and impact of the project at each stage of its life cycle. These indicators provide objective criteria for analysing various aspects of implementation, from resource use to sustainable impact. The correct selection and definition of these indicators ensure a comprehensive evaluation and provides both quantitative and qualitative data for decision-making and continuous improvement.

The European Commission establishes guides with indications on the indicators to be assessed by experts and provides guidance for beneficiaries on evaluation by using surveys, interviews and competency tests to assess impact (European Commission, 2025a, 2025b).

The main categories of indicators and their classification into quantitative and qualitative are detailed below.

3.1 Types of indicators

The indicators can be grouped into four groups, those oriented to the resources used in the project, those focused on the outputs or results obtained, the activities and processes and the long-term impacts. Firstly, the evaluation of resources ensures effective financial management and an adequate allocation of tools, critical aspects in European educational projects where the optimisation of resources is essential (Lázaro & Obregon, 2009). Secondly, the products generated constitute tangible evidence of the work carried out and help to evaluate whether the project meets the objectives of creating training resources (Owen, 2020). Third, process indicators are key to evaluating implementation in real time, allowing immediate adjustments and promoting quality in project development (Stufflebeam, 2014). Finally, assessing the long-term impact is essential to determine the success of a project, as it allows us to observe lasting change and effective knowledge transfer in the educational context (European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation et al., 2024; European Commission: European Parliament, 2017).

Based on the above, the types of indicators can be classified according to the resources used, the products generated, the activities and processes, and the long-term impacts (Table 1).

Table 1. Types of indicators

Resources used	Products generated	Activities and processes	Long-term impacts
They focus on evaluating the means used in the execution of the project, such as	They measure the concrete results produced by the project, such as teaching	They focus on the quantity and quality of the activities carried out, as well as on the	Sustainable effects of the project in the context where it is implemented, including

financial, material and technological. They are critical to ensuring that resources are used efficiently and in alignment with initial goals.	materials, learning guides, digital content and other resources that directly benefit the target audience	participation and commitment of those involved. This type of indicator allows the effectiveness of the implementation and the progress of the project to be analysed	the impact on acquired skills, the degree of use of the materials generated and the implementation of internships in educational institutions.
Examples: euros of financing obtained, percentage of co-financing, and use of technological tools	Examples: number of teaching materials created, percentage of increase in skills acquired by participants, guides or reference documents generated	Examples: number of training activities carried out, number of participants and their levels of progress, and level of skills acquired.	Examples: increases in professional skills (digital, linguistic, etc.), level of implementation of materials in the environment and frequency of use of the results.

Source: own elaboration

3.2 Quantitative and qualitative indicators

The classification of indicators into quantitative and qualitative (Table 2) allows for a more thorough evaluation, as each type of indicator offers distinct but complementary perspectives on project outcomes. Quantitative indicators are fundamental in the evaluation of projects because they provide clear and objective data, necessary to make decisions based on evidence (Chen, 2015), on the other hand, qualitative indicators allow for a deeper insight into the beneficiaries' experience and perception of quality (Patton, 2008), which is essential to interpret the results in a complex educational context.

Table 2. Quantitative and qualitative indicators

Quantitative	Qualitative
Quantitative indicators are those that can be measured numerically and provide accurate data on the achievement of objectives. These indicators are essential for objective and easily comparable results.	Qualitative indicators require interpretive analysis, as they reflect subjective aspects such as the perception of quality, the degree of satisfaction and the experience of the participants. These indicators are valuable for assessing intangible factors that also affect project outcomes

<p>Examples: number of accesses to digital resources, percentage increase in skills acquired, number of participants and hours of training</p>	<p>Examples: level of satisfaction of the participants, rating of the quality of the materials, perception of the impact of the project on the educational institutions</p>
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Source: own elaboration

The combination of quantitative and qualitative indicators provides a comprehensive evaluation tailored to the needs of the project. Both types of indicators are necessary to build a complete and accurate view of the progress and impact of the project, allowing project managers to make improvements based on concrete data and the experience of the beneficiaries.

4 Evaluation instruments

Measurement instruments are essential tools for collecting and analysing data that will allow the different indicators established in European educational projects to be evaluated. Each instrument is selected and designed based on the objectives of the project and the types of indicators defined (quantitative or qualitative), ensuring that the information obtained is relevant and useful for evaluating both processes and results. The main methods and instruments used in project evaluation are presented below, as well as specific examples of their implementation in the European educational context.

Mixed methods in research integrate the use of quantitative and qualitative data for a more complete evaluation using different instruments: surveys, interviews, and other data collection tools (Creswell, 2009, 2014; Creswell et al., 2011; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018; Dowding, 2013).

An evaluation approach focused on the practical use of results, addressing both evaluation instruments and the importance of observation and review of documents is useful in educational projects where detailed evaluation is required, with information of interest to decision-makers (Patton, 2008).

The European Commission itself carries out evaluations in the context of framework programmes such as Horizon Europe and Erasmus+ and provide information on the use of surveys, interviews and competence tests to assess the impact on beneficiaries of European education projects (European Commission,

2021, 2022; European Commission: European Parliament, 2017; European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation et al., 2024).

Therefore, the Systematic evaluation methods through the use of surveys, interviews and observations are especially useful in European education projects to apply standardized methods and collect reliable data (Cohen et al., 2013; Owen, 2020; Rossi et al., 2004; Scriven, 2003).

4.1 Examples of instruments

Table 3 shows some examples of instruments and how they could be used in the context of European educational projects.

Table 3. Examples of instruments

	Definition	Objective	Examples
Surveys	Surveys are an effective tool for collecting quantitative and qualitative data from a large number of participants. This instrument allows evaluating aspects such as satisfaction, the level of competencies achieved, and the perception of quality of the materials and activities of the project.	Surveys can be administered in person or online, adapting to the needs of the participants and facilitating the collection of structured data for statistical analysis	In European projects focused on improving digital skills, surveys can measure the level of student satisfaction with online teaching resources and assess the perceived impact on their technological skills
Interviews	Interviews offer a deeper qualitative approach, allowing the experience and perception of the participants to be explored in greater detail. Interviews can be individual or group and can vary in format, from semi-structured to open, depending on the type of information sought to be obtained.	This tool is particularly useful for obtaining detailed feedback on the impact of training activities and on the implementation of the outputs generated.	In an educational project that seeks to strengthen language competencies, interviews can help to understand the obstacles faced by students and the value they assign to the pedagogical practices introduced.

<p>Competency Tests</p>	<p>Competency tests are specific instruments to measure the level of skills acquired by participants according to the educational objectives of the project. These tests can be administered at the beginning and end of the project to assess progress in specific competencies.</p>	<p>The tests are usually structured and designed to generate numerical results that allow the levels of competence to be compared before and after the project intervention.</p>	<p>In a European digital skills project, tests can be applied before and after training activities to measure the increase in digital skills and analyse the direct impact of the intervention.</p>
<p>Observation Sheets</p>	<p>The observation sheets allow the collection of direct and objective data on the behavior, participation and level of commitment of the participants in training activities. This instrument is useful for evaluating both the implementation process and the response of the beneficiaries to pedagogical methods and resources.</p>	<p>Observations can be structured, with specific criteria, or open-ended, which allows flexibility to capture a variety of aspects in the interaction of participants with the project.</p>	<p>In projects that promote teamwork, observation sheets allow you to evaluate how students interact and how they apply the skills learned in group dynamics.</p>
<p>Review of Documents and Records</p>	<p>This method involves the systematic review of documents and records generated throughout the project, such as progress reports, meeting minutes, publications, and materials produced. It is a useful source of secondary data that complements the information obtained through other instruments.</p>	<p>The review of documents allows the fulfillment of the objectives, the production of resources and the quality of the products generated in the project to be evaluated.</p>	<p>Teaching materials, the review of documents allows us to evaluate whether they meet the proposed standards and objectives, and if they have been developed in the expected times.</p>

Source: own elaboration

4.2 Implementation examples

In the context of European educational projects, these instruments have been successfully employed to collect data in a systematic and structured way,

ensuring that the results are representative and reliable (Owen, 2020; Rossi et al., 2004). Below are some project ideas and possible measurement instruments that could be used, which when properly implemented, offer useful information to assess the impact, effectiveness and sustainability of European education projects.

4.2.1 Erasmus+ project on language skills

If a project is designed focused on improving language skills in multicultural contexts, surveys and interviews could be designed as evaluation methods to measure students' satisfaction with the materials and activities offered, as well as competency tests to assess their progress in language skills, before, during and after the project. The combination of these instruments can allow a complete evaluation of the impact of the project, both in terms of perception and measurable results.

4.2.2 Digital Education for Inclusion Project

In a European project dedicated to promoting digital inclusion among young people at risk of exclusion, observation sheets could be used to analyse the engagement of participants during training activities. In addition, apply digital skills tests to measure progress in the use of basic technological tools. The results can be completed with the review of progress documents and meeting minutes to assess the fulfillment of the project's objectives and the impact on social inclusion.

4.2.3 Horizon Europe project on pedagogical innovation

For a Horizon Europe project aimed at pedagogical innovation in STEM skills, surveys of teachers and students could be applied to assess the quality of the teaching materials generated and their impact on students' motivation towards science. Likewise, the review of documents will make it possible to analyse whether the materials respect the pedagogical standards and whether they are appropriately adapted to the educational environments of each participating country.

5 EFQM model and its application in project evaluation

The EFQM model is a widely used tool to evaluate and improve quality in organizations in different sectors, including education (Fonseca et al., 2021; Gabriela-Livia, 2021; Hakes, 2007; Martinez Mediano & Riopérez Losada, 2005; Nicolas & Del Castillo, 2020; Santos & Abreu, 2019). Its structure allows the identification of areas for improvement and the implementation of practices that increase the effectiveness and impact of projects. When applied in European educational projects, this model provides a flexible and robust structure to ensure that initiatives meet high quality standards and foster continuous improvement.

5.1 EFQM Model Description

The EFQM model was developed by the European Foundation for Quality Management as a comprehensive quality management framework. It is a tool that helps organizations measure their performance, identify strengths and areas for improvement, and apply corrective actions to optimize their processes.

Its structure is based on several criteria including leadership, strategy; people; resources and partnerships; processes, products and services; as well as the results in people, customers, society and business (Table 4).

Table 4. Key elements of the EFQM model

Leadership	How Well Organization Leaders Inspire and Drive a Culture of Improvement
Strategy	How the organization defines and deploys a strategy that supports its mission and vision
People	The organization's ability to manage and develop its human capital
Resources and Partnerships	Managing financial, technological and partnership resources to create value
Processes, products and services	How the organization designs and optimizes its processes to maximize value for beneficiaries
Results in people, customers, society and business	The results obtained are evaluated based on the impact on key groups, the satisfaction of the beneficiaries and the achievement of the objectives

Source: own elaboration

Each of these criteria is measured by several specific sub-criteria and practices, providing a detailed and systematic structure for evaluation and improvement. In the educational context, the EFQM model is particularly useful for managing and evaluating collaborative and development projects, such as European projects, due to its focus on social impact, leadership and efficiency in resource management.

5.2 Adaptation of the model to the context of European projects

The EFQM model, although applicable to multiple contexts, can be adapted to meet the specific needs of European educational projects (European Commission, 2018; European Commission. Directorate General for Development and Cooperation – EuropeAid., 2014). This adaptation involves adjusting their evaluation criteria and including indicators and methodologies that respond to the objectives of each project.

Figure 2. Common adaptations in the context of European projects (own elaboration)

Some of the common adaptations in the context of European projects are (Figure 2):

1. **Definition of specific indicators:** European projects often focus on improving educational skills and the creation of teaching resources. Specific indicators such as the degree of satisfaction of the beneficiaries, the number

of participants in training activities, and the increase in acquired skills can be added.

2. **Adapting the evaluation criteria to the needs of the beneficiaries:** the EFQM criteria can be modified to place a greater emphasis on learning outcomes and on creating value for the project's target audiences, such as students, teachers and educational institutions.
3. **Focus on sustainability and social impact:** In European projects, sustainability and long-term impact are key. The model can be adjusted to assess the degree of implementation of the teaching materials, the sustainable use of the resources generated, and the impact on the educational environment and on the competencies of the beneficiaries.
4. **Adjusting monitoring and continuous evaluation:** The EFQM model encourages continuous evaluation through regular reviews. In the context of European projects, this translates into a formative follow-up to ensure that the project meets its objectives in each phase and adjusts when necessary, following an evidence-based methodology.

5.3 Benefits of the EFQM model

The application of the EFQM model in the evaluation of European educational projects offers multiple benefits, which are detailed below (Martinez Mediano & Riopérez Losada, 2005; Sütőová et al., 2022; Taraza et al., 2024):

1. **Continuous improvement:** one of the fundamental principles of the EFQM model is to foster a culture of continuous improvement. This is especially relevant in educational projects, as it allows learning from each stage of the project and applying this knowledge to optimize future initiatives. With the EFQM model, institutions can continuously review and adjust their practices to ensure they meet quality expectations.
2. **Structured evaluation:** The EFQM model provides a clear and detailed structure for evaluation, with well-defined criteria ranging from leadership to bottom line. This structure helps institutions to organise their evaluation processes in a systematic way, covering all critical aspects of European projects and ensuring a full analysis of the impact and effectiveness of the project.

3. **Compliance with quality standards:** the implementation of the EFQM model ensures that projects meet high quality standards at European level. This is essential in educational projects funded by the European Union, where transparency and quality are fundamental requirements for funding and recognition.
4. **Fostering responsibility and transparency:** The EFQM model promotes accountability by generating reports and evaluations that show the results achieved and areas for improvement. This is particularly important in European projects, where a justification of the use of resources and the impacts achieved is required to ensure transparency in the management of public funds.
5. **Comparability and replicability of projects:** by using a standardised model such as EFQM, institutions can compare their results and practices with other similar projects in Europe. This allows the identification of best practices and facilitates the replicability of successful projects in different educational contexts, contributing to the development of quality European education.

In conclusion, the EFQM model is a valuable tool for the evaluation of European educational projects, as it provides a solid structure to measure and improve quality at each stage of the project. Adapted to the educational context and the specific needs of each project, the EFQM model helps to ensure that projects achieve their objectives, foster a culture of continuous improvement and deliver high-impact results in the European educational field.

6 Case Studies

The analysis carried out in the projects of the doctoral thesis "Methodological guide for the successful use of digital technologies in education: improving learning through European educational projects" (Alonso de Castro, 2020, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c; Alonso de Castro & García-Peñalvo, 2024) reveals that evaluation in European projects, both in their initial, formative and final stages, as well as in their impact in the medium and long term, is an aspect that is generally insufficiently defined.

A noteworthy aspect is that, in most of the cases analysed, once the mandatory years of dissemination have elapsed, the websites associated with these projects

stop being updated and, in many cases, even cease to be operational. This fact is especially striking, considering that these are projects catalogued as examples of good practice.

This phenomenon reflects a recurrent lack in the evaluations of European project proposals, where there are few projects that incorporate a clear, rigorous and systematic design of the evaluation processes. This includes not only formative and summative evaluation, but also the analysis of the impact generated, both in the participating institutions and in other similar ones that could benefit from the results of the project.

However, it is important to highlight that the identification of instruments depended mainly on the project websites and the information available on the Erasmus+ Programme Results Platform (<https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/projects>). Consequently, the results obtained are conditioned by the availability, stability and quality of public materials: the deactivation of web pages, broken links or domain migrations can hide existing evidence. Therefore, the absence of evidence in open sources does not necessarily imply an absence of evaluation. In addition, heterogeneities (language of publication, institutional practices and line of action —KA, HE, etc.—) concur that introduce variation in the depth and format of the documentation. This analysis does not weight by size or budget of the projects and does not include meta-analysis of effects; Its purpose is methodological-documentary and oriented to the transfer of effectively published evaluation practices.

6.1 Extraction and Coding Protocol

To analyse the evaluation techniques of the projects that are the subject of the aforementioned doctoral thesis, a protocol was applied with two complementary planes: extraction and coding. For each case, a record sheet was prepared where the metadata of the project, the accessibility and persistence of its results, the published evaluation instruments (type, time of application and target population), the specified indicators and the evidence of results, impact and sustainability were collected. The degree of openness (licenses, DOIs and deposits in repositories) was also noted.

In the coding phase, the information was organized with deductive categories based on consolidated frameworks such as: the Context, Inputs, Process, Output (CIPP) model of Stufflebeam (2014), the use-oriented evaluation (UFE) of Patton (2008) and the logical model of the Chen (2015), as well as the European Commission's evaluation guides (European Commission, 2025a, 2025b) — and we combined them with inductive categories that emerged from the cases themselves: usability, initial diagnosis, formative follow-up in the classroom, achievement tests and comprehensive methodological evaluation.

This mixed approach, with a convergent design, has made it possible to triangulate each instrument with the moment of the evaluation cycle (initial, formative, summative) and with the level of evidence (process, results, impact), improving interpretation and comparability between cases.

6.2 Projects analysed

If we take into account the thirteen projects that passed all the phases of the research of the aforementioned thesis (Alonso De Castro, 2023c), because it is a good practice and is still active at the time of research with an impact on students and teachers, only seven (53.8 %) published identifiable evaluation instruments or protocols (Table 5). This restricts transparency, replicability, and learning between projects.

Table 5. Projects that have published evaluation instruments as results

Title (in English)	Code	Published information about the evaluation
Education in Mathematics in Game-based Immersive Contexts	2017-1-PT01-KA201-035847	Usability tests (students, teachers, partners); Classroom Observation Activity
Choose Your Future	2014-1-BG01-KA201-001435	Course Tests
Development of skills through art and emotional intelligence, to improve learning and situations of social exclusion	2015-1-ES01-KA201-016210	Methodological document of the evaluation with the model, indicators and tools, results, evaluation of the meetings and evaluation of the work in the schools
Take the e+train	2017-1-ES01-KA219-038105	Initial needs study
Innovative Education towards Sustainable Food Systems	2016-1-PL01-KA203-026652	Student Knowledge Survey
Massive open online courses with videos for palliative clinical field and	2014-1-RO01-KA203-002940	Starting Point Research

intercultural and multilingual medical communication		
Developing Skills in Dealing with Emergencies: Civil protection for people	2017-1-EL01-KA204-036189	Civil Protection Knowledge Survey

Source: own elaboration

6.3 Distribution of the type of evidence

The distribution of the types of published evidence is presented in Table 6 and, in summary, is as follows:

- **Usability and classroom observation:** 1 case (usability tests with students, teachers and partners; observation activity).
- **Tests linked to the training action:** 1 case (course tests).
- **Comprehensive methodological evaluation** (model + indicators + tools + results + evaluation of meetings and work in centres): 1 case.
- **Initial diagnosis / needs study:** 2 cases.
- **Thematic knowledge surveys** (specific competences: sustainable food, civil protection): 2 cases.

Overall, immediate outcome, diagnosis or achievement, and process instruments, oriented towards usability or observation, predominate, while there is very little public evidence of sustained impact and external evaluation.

From this information, several cross-cutting conclusions can be drawn about the quality of the evidence. To begin with, in terms of **cycle coverage**, most projects that publish instruments document only **one** phase (diagnosis or achievement), less frequently **two** (e.g. diagnosis and final evaluation) and rarely all **three** with an explicit programme logic.

With regard to the **operational definition of the indicators**, those of **product** and **process** predominate, while those that capture **medium-term impact** (actual implementation in schools, changes in teaching practice, replications) and **sustainability** (continued use of the results at 12–24 months) are scarce.

The **methodological quality stated** is also limited: it is rare for evidence on **validity, reliability or sampling procedures to be published**; when they are made explicit, the usefulness of the evidence for third parties increases significantly.

Finally, **openness and persistence** remain the exception: the publication of instruments (surveys, rubrics, observation guides), **codebooks** and **anonymized datasets** with open licenses and DOIs is still in the minority, and the disappearance of **websites** it weakens reproducibility and transfer. These patterns were already anticipated in the original manuscript and are confirmed in the systematic review of cases.

Table 6. Matrix of correspondences "type of instrument ↔ phase of the cycle"

Published instrument type	Sample project using it	Predominant phase	Value added	Usual gap
Needs study / initial diagnosis	<i>Take the e+train.</i>	Initial	Align design with real needs	Few explicit connections to impact indicators
	<i>MOOC—palliatives and intercultural mediation</i>			
Knowledge Survey	<i>Sustainable food systems.</i>	Initial and/or End	Allows pre-post if repeated	Rarely reported reliability/validity
	<i>Civil defence</i>			
Course Tests	<i>Choose Your Future</i>	Final (summative)	Evidence of achievement in the course itself	"Opportunity" measurement risk without baseline
Usability + classroom observation	<i>Education in Mathematics in Game-based Immersive Contexts</i>	Formative	Iterative improvement of didactic design	It is difficult to link to impact beyond the classroom
Comprehensive methodological document (model + indicators + tools + results)	<i>Art & Emotional Intelligence</i>	Cross-cutting	High traceability and replicability	Rare in the sample

Source: own elaboration

6.4 Derived practical recommendations

To close the gap between "good practice" and useful and traceable evaluative evidence, a minimum evaluation package aligned with the Erasmus+ Guide is proposed (European Commission, 2025a, 2025b) and the CIPP/U-FE frameworks.

It is recommended that a **concise project logic model** be made explicit, listing assumptions, intermediate results and **indicators by level** – resources, activities, outputs, results and impact.

Where appropriate, incorporate a **lightweight pre-post design** (e.g. for digital or language skills), using **open instruments** and their **codebook**; if this is not feasible, opt for a **simple quasi-experimental comparison** with **natural groups**.

Formative **monitoring** should be documented — usability testing, structured observation, and micro-cycles of improvement — and supported by **shared rubrics**.

Impact and sustainability indicators should include, at a minimum, curricular adoption, use of 6-, 12- and 24-month materials, training of trainers and verifiable reuses.

In terms of **data management and openness**, it is advisable to have a **management plan (DMP)** and deposit anonymized instruments, scripts and **datasets** in repositories such as **Zenodo** (<https://zenodo.org/>) or **OSF** (<https://osf.io/>), with **DOI**, **open license** and **FAIR** metadata (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable), linking them from the **Results Platform**. Finally, to ensure **persistence**, it is advisable to clone the **results site** to a static repository (e.g. **GitHub Pages** with Zenodo DOI) to avoid the website going down after the project is finished.

7 Discussion and conclusions

Continuous and final evaluation in European education projects is essential to ensure that initiatives meet their objectives and maximise their impact. This evaluation process, which ranges from the definition of objectives to the measurement of final impacts, allows managers to adjust during its development, achieving a better alignment with the needs of the beneficiaries and the objectives of the project. In addition, the implementation of structured and systematized evaluations helps institutions learn from each project, improve their internal processes, and adopt best practices. In short, project evaluation not only contributes to transparency and effectiveness in execution but also strengthens the organization's ability to develop quality projects in the future.

However, the analysis of the registered European projects of the Erasmus+ programme shows a lack of systematic procedures for evaluation. In many cases,

the implementation of a structured framework that allows the monitoring, measurement and analysis of the results achieved throughout the life of the project is not observed. This lack of systematicity also includes the evaluation of the impact that these projects have on the participating institutions, which limits the ability to identify significant changes or improvements derived from the initiatives. The lack of monitoring and detailed impact analysis hinders not only accountability, but also the possibility of replicating or scaling up good practices in other educational or research contexts. This underlines the importance of integrating evaluation as a central component in the design and implementation of European projects.

7.1 Limitations

Despite its benefits, evaluation in European projects faces some limitations. First, the diversity of contexts and participants in these projects can make it difficult to standardize indicators, complicating comparability of results and impact evaluation. Second, many projects face time and resource constraints, which can limit the ability to conduct a thorough and ongoing evaluation. To address these limitations, it is recommended:

- **Adapt indicators to specific contexts:** develop indicators tailored to local and cultural realities, which will increase the relevance and accuracy of evaluation in multicultural and multi-institutional projects.
- **Promote evaluation training:** invest in the training of project teams to develop skills in evaluation methods and data management.
- **Provide standard evaluation tools and resources:** Develop accessible evaluation tools and software that facilitate data collection and analysis, reducing time and resource barriers.

7.2 Practical implications

The experience gained through the evaluation indicators and the EFQM model suggests that these approaches can be applied in other European educational projects. The adaptability of the EFQM model, together with the structured definition of indicators, allows project coordinators to evaluate and improve projects on an ongoing basis, benefiting both the project recipients and the funding agencies.

Some practical recommendations for applying these elements in other projects include:

- **Establishment of an early evaluation process:** initiate the design of indicators and define evaluation instruments in the early phases of the project, which allows continuous monitoring and a better response to possible deviations.
- **Fostering collaboration and learning between projects:** taking advantage of the structure of the EFQM model to compare results between different European projects, allowing successful learning and practices to be shared.
- **Use of digital technologies in evaluation:** Invest in digital tools for data collection and analysis, which facilitates real-time monitoring and improves data accuracy.

In conclusion, a well-structured evaluation, supported by models such as the EFQM and adapted indicators, is essential to maximise the impact of European projects in the education sector. This contributes to the creation of more effective educational initiatives with sustainable results that respond to the needs of an educational community in constant change and expansion. Finally, this model not only applies to projects at the European level but is also extensible to any educational project that seeks to maximise impact and applicability in the medium and long term.

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